

Theoretical language issues

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THE DIFFERENTIATION OF ACADEMIC AND GENERAL ENGLISH**Abstract**

The article features the similarities and distinctions between Academic and General English. The present paper also highlights the role of both types of English in language teaching practice. Academic English is a certain view of English which is essential in the world of research, study and universities whereas General English is a type of English through which people communicate each other in their everyday lives.

Key Words: Academic English, General English, distinction, similarity, vocabulary, specialized area, APA style

Academic English can be viewed as Formal English whereas Informal/Basic/Social English is appropriate while defining General English. This means if a learner needs English only for communication in his or her social life, General English is advised to learn. For other purposes, for instance, working or studying in academic sphere the learner has to acquire Academic English. However, Kitkauskiene (2006) asserts in both cases the learner is required to learn General English since Academic English is based on the knowledge of it; therefore both types should not be opposed to each other. Charles and Pecorary (2016) analyze the vocabulary of academic texts and essays and conclude that the distinction of Academic and General English is not absolute.

Major similarities of Academic and General English are that both of them can develop one's ability to communicate in oral or written form and that their adjacent elements are not perceptibly different from each other's which makes a continuum between them. Kitkauskiene (2006) notes "In both cases linguistic knowledge includes the correctness of grammatical structures, proper choice of words and precision of their meaning" (p. 89). However, there are some significant differences between Academic and General English. In contrast to General English, Academic English possess the following characteristics: more formal; more objective; more advanced grammar structures; avoiding the use of idioms and

slangs; implementing references to other writers; frequent use of passive verbs; developing well-structured texts and paragraphs; the use of linking words which provide the text cohesion. Furthermore, there are language-specific features in academic English that are almost distinctive from general English. More complex usage of grammar (tenses, complex sentence structure, nouns, adjective clauses, syntax, and referencing) is commonly seen in academic texts. Frequent utilization of present and past tenses along with other specifications makes academic writing genres differ from general genres like fiction (Biber, Johansson, Leech, Conrad, & Finegan, 1999). However, it is impossible to say that academic and general English are completely different from each other. There are a few academic text-specific words, and what makes them unique is their frequency of occurrence. For example, some words occur more frequently in an academic context than in a general one. Gardner and Davies (2014) declare that just over 14% of the terms in high academic writing are from this core academic lexicon. Therefore, academic achievement is impossible without a broad understanding of general English. The differences and similarities between academic and general English since they are clearly analyzed with regard to vocabulary, grammar and frequent occurrence in certain domains.

On the other side, there are some points about academic English which can be worth recognizing. First, academic English has a formal tone, proper grammar and the avoidance of contractions, which makes it different from general English. For example, when we talk to our boss or write a letter to him, we tend to be more formal. Second of all, unlike general English, academic English possess technical vocabulary relevant specific areas. This means biology students must acquire academic skills as well as biology terminology. Another feature is academic formatting and style rules. We all know essay writing in IELTS requires specific formatting, and styles such as APA and MLA are the next characteristics of academic English. Last but not least, academic writing requires references and quotations as we can see in this discussion. General English is mostly taught at school while academic English is in higher education. In this regard, teaching English can be divided into two spheres: English for General Purposes (EGP) and English for Academic Purposes (EAP). Also, as for Widdowson (1983 cited in Ajideh, 2009) the difference between EAP and EGP lies in the way we define and implement learning purposes. EAP is objected – oriented compared to EGP that can be attributed by aim- oriented which does not require the

specification for the learners and teachers. While evaluating relevant language skills EGP teachers and graduate learners do not appropriately set the goals. They may have restrictive competence facing defined tasks (Robinson, 1991, p.80).

To sum up, it seems that academic English has more strict rules than general English. It is highly recommended that graduate students and EAP teachers should know the similarities and differences cited above. The former are expected to be competent to use English in academic context, while the distinction has some vital implications for the latter. Raising awareness of this insight is critically important as an EAP practitioner is responsible for performing certain special roles, for example, as a course designer, material provider, collaborator, researcher, evaluator and cultural interpreter along with the role of a language teacher.

References

- Biber, D., Johansson, S., Leech, G., Conrad, S., & Finegan, E. (1999). *Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English*. Harlow, Pearson Education Limited.
- Charles, M. and Pecorary, D. (2016). *Introducing English for Academic Purposes*. NY. Routledge.
- Gardner, D., and Davies, M. (2014). *A new academic vocabulary list*. Applied Linguistics
- Kitkauskiene, L. (2006). *General English and English for Specific Purposes (ESP)*. Vilnius Gediminas Technical University.
- Ajideh , P. (2009). *Autonomous Learning and Metacognitive Strategies in ESP Class*.
- Robinson, P. (1991) *ESP Today: A Practitioner's Guide*, Hertfordshire, Prentice Hall.
- Widdoson, H.G. (1983). *Learning Purpose and Language Use*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.